

Reaction of Various Amino-Substituted Nitrogen Heterocyclics with α -Bromoketones

J. V. SINGH

Department of Explosives, Pub-Sarania, Gauhati-3.

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A hitherto unreported heterocyclic system imidazo (2, 1-b)- naphthothiazole (I) has been synthesised by the reaction of various α -bromoketones with 2-aminonaphtho (2, 1-d) thiazole. Various other known condensed imidazo-heterocyclic systems with 2-benzothiazolyl substitution are also reported.

VARIOUS ring systems containing $\text{—C}(\text{NH}_2)\text{=N—}$ as a part of the ring have been found to condense with α -bromoketones to yield various condensed

I (R = H or methyl) by the reaction of 2-aminonaphtho (2, 1-d)-thiazole with chloroacetaldehyde diethyl acetal or chloroacetone gave a gelatinous mass which could not be purified.

imidazo heterocyclic systems, the halogen attacking the ring nitrogen rather than the primary amino group¹. Imidazo (2,1-b) benzothiazole (II)², imidazo (1,2-a) pyridine (III)^{1,3} and imidazo (1,2-a) pyrimidine (IV)³ are the well-known condensed imidazo heterocyclic systems thus prepared. No attempt has yet been made to synthesise imidazo (2, 1-b) naphtho (2,1-d) thiazole (I). In the present communication, we wish to report the synthesis of I (R= aryl or 2 benzothiazolyl) starting from 2-aminonaphtho (2, 1-d) thiazole. Compounds II, III, IV (R= 2-benzothiazolyl) were also synthesised by the reaction of corresponding 2-amino derivatives with 2-benzothiazolyl-bromomethyl ketone, prepared by the method of Sawhney and Singh⁴. For the present purpose, 2-aminonaphtho (2,1-d) thiazole and 6-substituted-2-aminobenzothiazoles were prepared by the method of Kaufmann⁵. An attempt to synthesise

General Procedure :

To a solution of the appropriate 2-amino heterocyclic compound (0.01 mole) in alcohol (20 ml.) was added a solution of the appropriate α -bromoketone (0.01 mole) in alcohol (20 ml.) and the mixture heated under reflux for 5 hrs. On cooling, a crystalline solid separated which was collected by filtration and washed with little alcohol. It was then treated with a dilute solution of ammonia, filtered, washed with water and dried. It was crystallised from dimethylformamide.

The physical properties and analytical details are given in Table-1.

TABLE 1—CONDENSED IMIDAZO-HETEROCYCLIC COMPOUNDS.*

Sr. No.	Structure No.	R	R'	m. p.** °C	Yield %	Mol. formula	Found (%)		Reqd. (%)	
							S	N	S	N
1.	I	Phenyl	—	234	58	C ₁₉ H ₁₂ N ₂ S	10.49	9.12	10.66	9.33
2.	I	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	—	238	62	C ₁₉ H ₁₁ ClN ₂ S	9.63	8.14	9.57	8.37
3.	I	<i>p</i> -Bromophenyl	—	248	51	C ₁₉ H ₁₁ BrN ₂ S	8.13	7.58	8.44	7.39
4.	I	2-Benzothiazolyl	—	285	48	C ₂₀ H ₁₁ N ₃ S ₂	18.07	11.62	17.93	11.76
5.	II	2-Benzothiazolyl	H	225	52	C ₁₈ H ₉ N ₃ S ₂	20.71	13.14	20.85	13.68
6.	II	2-Benzothiazolyl	Chloro	255	43	C ₁₈ H ₉ ClN ₃ S ₂	19.19	12.63	18.74	12.30
7.	II	2-Benzothiazolyl	Methyl	220	51	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ N ₃ S ₂	19.50	12.56	19.94	13.09
8.	II	2-Benzothiazolyl	Methoxy	241	48	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ N ₃ S ₂ O	18.51	12.29	18.99	12.46
9.	III	2-Benzothiazolyl	—	290	40	C ₁₄ H ₉ N ₃ S	12.25	16.42	12.75	16.73
10.	IV	2-Benzothiazolyl	—	300	46	C ₁₃ H ₈ N ₄ S	12.46	22.49	12.70	22.22

* None of the compounds showed any absorption in the regions 3100-3500 cm⁻¹ and 1600-1750cm⁻¹ in the IR-spectra taken in Nujol-mull.

** All the melting points, taken in heating bath are uncorrected.

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